

ECONOMICS

IMPROVEMENT PROCESSES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF RENEWABLE ENERGY IN TAJIKISTAN

Muminov P.

*Tajik Technical University named after academician M.S. Osimi,
Master's student*

Abstract

Launching and promoting the construction of small and medium power plants using solar and wind energy can partially eliminate the existing seasonal shortages of electricity, which the population of Tajikistan suffers from shortages in certain periods of the year. Of course, for this, the geographical position of the Republic, which is abundant and rich in solar power resources and wind density necessary for renewable energy, and which is called the “golden belt” of the sun by international geographers and meteorologists, was effectively used.

Keywords: Renewable Energy, Energy, Tajikistan.

According to the indicators of the Ministry of Energy and Water Resources of Tajikistan in 2021, up to 96.0% of the total energy (electricity) produced will be “green energy”. This indicator represents Tajikistan in the position of implementation of the “green economy” process in the field of energy at the world level in one of the first places.

Taking into account the existing and estimated potential of solar energy and wind resources in the Republic, it is reasonable to conclude that currently such resources, which can be the source and the main reason for the lack of electricity in the mountainous parts of Tajikistan, are not being used effectively. Considering the fact that in Tajikistan, the number of days of use of sunlight is not less than 300 days, the available indicators for the available resources are very insufficient.

In Tajikistan, there are also projects implemented in this direction with the direct financial support of such international organizations as USAID, UNDP, ABD, JICA and the US Embassy together with the Ministry of Energy and Water of the Republic, JSC “Sistemavtomatika”, JSC “Renewable Energy Association of Tajikistan” “TGEM” and others are doing. These financial and development partners are implementing various projects in the field of renewable sources in remote and mountainous regions of Tajikistan, partly from their own funds and allocated grants.

According to the published data, the temperature of the Earth's globe is increasing every year under the influence of certain factors (1), which can also lead to droughts and negative results of water power plants. Especially in the last decades in the existing domestic rivers, which provide power with such resources, insufficiency is practically observed in certain periods of the year and has a negative effect on the full supply of electricity.

In the near future, the results of the influence of such existing factors may also have a “social impact”. Therefore, in order to reduce the negative results of their influence and prevent foreseeable risks from the influence of such factors, it is necessary to implement a far-sighted economic policy of diversification of electricity production industries. It is the consideration of this point in this year's Message of the President of Tajikistan “... rapid industrialization, use of innovative

technologies...” (2). Therefore, over time, the construction and operation of small and medium-sized power plants of renewable energy are alternative sources.

International experience shows that in order to reduce emissions and environmental pollution in many developed countries, in order to develop the renewable energy industries through the operation of solar, wind and other renewable energy sources, a special certificate (or green certificate itself) is issued. The existence and implementation of such a Certificate can implement a new element (element) of the market, i.e. purchase and sale of these Certificates.

The existence of this certificate gives renewable energy producers a number of privileges in the use of financial resources (loans), preferential loans, the use of the mechanism for delaying the payment of investment tax (investment tax credit), exemption from certain types of taxes and these privileges. It makes incentives and economic results for such sources more effective and, above all, it increases the attraction of foreign investment.

The Tax Code of the Republic of Tajikistan in the new edition, which came into use on 01.01.2022, provides for some benefits, tax reliefs, taking into account the international best practice of encouraging development partners, domestic and foreign investors to produce energy from renewable sources.

The form of delaying the payment of the investment tax (investment tax credit), exemption from some types of taxes on the import of devices or their domestic production can help the development of solar and wind power plants and increase the economic incentive for investment. In today's market of services for the use of energy from renewable sources, existing state structures, legal and real persons participate directly or indirectly.

The relationship between producers and consumers, the procedure for using energy produced by solar and wind energy, is provided for in the Law of the Republic of Tajikistan “On the use of renewable energy sources” (No. 587, dated 12.01.2010). Currently, due to the division of the energy structure of the Republic with the structures of production, transmission and sale, it requires a new view on the payment and compensation of costs of renewable energy.

Taking into account the available resources and the recognition of Tajikistan in the United Nations program as a pilot country for “Sustainable energy for all”, it can raise the current position of the Republic in comparison with the countries of the Central Asian region in the production of electricity from renewable sources.

Today’s experience shows that the production of electricity from renewable sources is being implemented in a number of countries of the Central Asian region, including the Republic of Uzbekistan, with the support and direct contribution of state structures, modern and technologically advanced projects. According to the developed plans, by the end of 2025, the share of electricity from such sources in the total amount of electricity production is expected to increase to 25.0% (3).

In order to implement these projects at the state level, the legislation “On partnership between the state and the private sector” has been adopted, which creates conditions for accelerating the implementation of renewable energy projects with the participation of state structures, foreign and domestic investors. Also, for a certain period, these enterprises are exempted from paying taxes such as property tax, land tax, income tax and are provided with a number of privileges and advantages, as well as the procedure for connecting to the energy structure and using electricity from such sources.

In today’s development and promotion of renewable energy sources, new technologies are emerging

every day. The need to purchase, import and use in the Republic the existing opportunities for the assessment of the existing sources (sources) will make it clear and clear, the compiled album of solar areas and measurements, the assessment of wind density positions, will be better studied and the necessary changes and additions will be made. entered and their statistics should be promoted. The availability of such necessary and accurate information, in our opinion, can stimulate the interest of development partners and foreign and domestic investors in such projects.

During the development of renewable energy resources, the construction of small and medium-sized power plants, especially for the purpose of promotion and development of a new branch of the economy, the relevant structures should conduct the necessary activities to promote work with consumers and present such existing plans and projects with donors (financial partners), technical experts. through the work of the Internet network, conducting international conferences and forums.

References

1. Global Energy Trends - 2021 Edition
2. Message of the President of the Republic of Tajikistan to the Majlisi Oli dated 21.12.2021.
3. Materials received by the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Uzbekistan.